

The relationship between formative assessment ability on uses of the flipped classroom model in teaching lower Secondary Schools in Northern Region Zanzibar Tanzania

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Abstract

The study was carried out to assess the relationship between formative assessment and flipped classroom model; the study employed a cross-sectional survey design using mixed methods approaches. A total of 400 respondents participated in the study and census sampling was employed since the entire population was used, questionnaires and interview guide were the instruments used for data collection, the instrument was validated and there was a reliability coefficient of 0.98. The data was analyzed using frequency, percentage, means and standard deviation. Spearman Rank Correlation analysis was used to analyze the relationship of variable at 0.05 level of significance, Interview was analyze using content analysis. The findings of this study revealed that the there is a significant relationship between formative assessment and flipped class room model. Based on the findings and conclusions the following recommendations were made: that teachers should offer refresher courses, there is need for head teachers to encourage teachers not only to stick on the flipped classroom alone but also to balance flipped classroom with face-to-face teaching also. The Education Board especially in Zanzibar should ensure that teachers are monitored regularly and post-supervision conference is always arranged, the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training should emphasize increasing sensitization, update courses, provide training and seminars, motivation of teachers, improve infrastructure and use of technology especially in hardship area/environment.

Keywords: Formative; Assessment; Flipped; Classroom; Model; Teaching, Lower; Secondary; Schools

1. Introduction

The focus of classroom teaching and learning processes has remained the same, enabling students to memorize the facts taught and reproduce them in examinations to qualify for further studies and formal jobs. It has been observed further that, the majority of teachers have a narrow understanding of competency-based curriculum and poor pedagogical skills due to little or no training on competency-based curriculum, hence, the use of traditional methods of teaching and assessment is still dominant. This suggests that teachers in both primary and secondary schools are not implementing a competency-based curriculum. Way Long Quek (2017), Stuebar and Idowu (2019), Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023), Maila and Asiimwe (2024) showed that teachers lack motivation, competencies, and an understanding of the policy requirements. Along the same lines Sornson, Kirby and Martin (2016), Lindermann and Mathics (2017), Neapane (2017), Kayindu and Asiimwe, (2020), Epra (2021), Epra and Ecen (2021), Apiku and Asiimwe (2023) found that a majority of teachers were not aware of the matters accompanied with the competence based curriculum. Their practices in the classroom did not show that they implement effectively the operating curriculum (Apiku, 2023; Asiimwe & Zueana, 2023; Mugenyi, Matagi, Kobusingye & Asiimwe, 2023).

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Additionally, Way Long Quek (2017), Stuebar and Idowu (2019), Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023), Maila and Asiimwe (2024) noted that Competent Based Curriculum (CBC) equips learners with skills to learn, learning how to learn, performing tasks, and working in collaboration with one another. Tanzania established a competence-based education curriculum for lower secondary education and compulsory implementation. Therefore, this study deeply studied the opinions of school heads and teachers on clinical supervision practices in lower secondary education because it is an important stage of formal education for preparing human resources for the world market. A Review of Teacher Preparation in Tanzania (2005), enhanced the School-Based Instructional Supervision Capacity (SBISC) of the school leaders for the implementation of Competence-Based Curriculum in Zanzibar. It was conducted in the West Urban Region, and particularly at the Urban and West B district schools in Zanzibar under (Komba and Mwandaji, 2015; Way Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023; & Chuk, Asiimwe & Asiimwe, 2023). The study was prompted by the massive empirical evidence from the literature suggesting that the implementation of the CBC in Tanzania remains problematic despite its operation for nearly fifteen years now. Findings from the preliminary investigation indicated that school leaders failed to guide teachers on competence-based instructional planning, competence-based instructional delivery in the classroom, and competence-based assessment. Thus, intervention research was deemed necessary to empower school leaders to enhance their School-Based Instructional Supervision Capacity (Komba and Mwandaji 2015; Way Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023).

2. Theory and Related Literature

Teacher assessment model and uses of flipped classroom model is an important for middle level teachers and their students. Way Long Quek (2017), Stuebar and Idowu (2019), Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023), studied about curriculum, instruction, and *assessment* that were interrelated and highlighted that the intention of this summary is to establish assessment's rightful position as one priority for middle grade teachers and their students. When used wisely and well, teachers obtain information about their students' strengths and needs, and their students remain informed about their achievements. The study found out that, good assessment practices include both formative and summative assessments. In concert, they offer local and global evidence that teaching and learning are progressing. Formative assessments direct teachers' day-to-day decisions while summative assessments assuage a broader base of educational stakeholders that the attainments of our nation's youth meet local, national, and global expectations (Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023). Attaining a strong and coherent relationship between verifying local gains and confirming national competitiveness demands careful attention to the data obtained from formative and summative options to attain a comprehensive and thoughtful. Way Long Quek (2017), Stuebar and Idowu (2019), Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023), studied on teachers throughout the learning process correlated to teacher assessment competence and uses of flipped classroom model the study revealed that, formative assessment consists of a range of formal and informal diagnostic testing procedures, conducted by teachers during the learning process, for modifying teaching and adapting activities to improve student attainment. Systemic interventions such as Response to Intervention and Data-Based Decision making depend heavily on the use of formative assessment (Komba and Mwandaji 2015; Way Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023).

The current educational climate emphasizes school accountability through standardized test scores as the primary method for determining an effective learning environment. Federal, state, and local educational policy requires that schools and classrooms should be held more responsible for the outcomes they produce (example, student achievement). However, the process for ensuring accountability rests on standardized testing of children, typically starting in third grade (Komba and Mwandaji 2015; Way Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023). The focus on accountability and standardized testing should not confuse the contribution that the social quality of teacher – student relationships has on academic development contend that strong student- teacher relationships “provide a unique entry point for educators working to improve the social and learning environments of schools and classrooms (Komba and Mwandaji 2015; Way Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Rasmussen (2013) investigated the effects of the flipped classroom model on academic performance of high school advanced placement students perceptions it is linked to teacher assessment competence and uses of flipped classroom model.

The control group consisted of students from the 2011-2012 academic years, in which traditional teaching methods were used. The treatment group consisted of students from the 2012-13 academic years, in which the flipped classroom approach was used. Identical assessments were administered and analyzed through both descriptive statistics and independent t-tests. A statistically significant difference was found on all assessments with the flipped class students performing higher on average. In addition, most students had a favourable perception about the flipped classroom noting the ability to pause, rewind, and review lectures, as well as increased individualized learning, and increased

teacher availability. Way Long Quek (2017), Stuebar and Idowu (2019), Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023) discovered that using flipped class leads to an increase in students' performance and emphasized that flipping the class room was not about creating more work for the students, but changing the type of work that students do at home and changing the class experience.

Also, Way Long Quek (2017), Stuebar and Idowu (2019), Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023), Asiimwe and Magunda (2023) conducted a study on "Intentional on Teacher Assessment Literacy: A Review of Standards and Measures Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability" correlates teacher assessment competence and use of flipped classroom model, revealed that assessment literacy is a core professional requirement across educational systems. Hence, measuring and supporting teachers' assessment literacy has been a primary focus over the past two decades. At present, there are a multitude of assessment standards across the world and numerous assessment literacy measures that represent different conceptions of assessment literacy. The purpose of the research is to (a) analyses assessment literacy lower level and (b) analyses prominent assessment literacy measures developed after 1990. Through a thematic analysis of 15 assessment standards and an examination of 8 assessment literacy measures, results indicate noticeable shifts in standards over time yet the majority of measures continue to be based on early conceptions of assessment literacy. Results also serve to define the multiple dimensions of assessment literacy and yield important recommendations for measuring teacher assessment literacy.

In the study conducted by Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023), Maila and Asiimwe (2024) found that teacher assessment competency in educational assessment is a professional requirement within the current accountability framework of public education across many parts of the world. Assessment literacy involves the ability to construct reliable assessments, and then administer and score these assessments to facilitate valid instructional decisions anchored to state or provincial educational standards (Komba and Mwandaji 2015; Way Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023).

Recent policy developments throughout North America, Europe, Australia, and New Zealand have emphasized classroom teachers' ongoing formative and summative assessments to guide instruction and support student learning. Further, empirical studies have demonstrated significant gains in student achievement, metacognitive functions, and motivation for learning when teachers integrate assessment with their instruction (Komba and Mwandaji 2015; Way Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023). While, Way Long Que (2017) through their Systematic Review of the Psychometric Properties Assessment Literacy Measures, found that despite assessment literacy being a national priority in the US and a keystone component of teacher evaluation that narrate to teacher assessment competence and uses of flipped classroom model, and that Teacher Assessment Literacy existing measures maintain weak evidence across reliability and validity indicators of: test content, internal consistency reliability, score stability, and association with student outcomes.

Long Que (2017) Stuebar and Idowu (2019) Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022) conclude that in order to increase the validity of assessment literacy measures researchers must begin by examining the "representativeness and relevance of content in light of transformations in the assessment landscape (examples accountability systems, conceptions of formative assessment). However, (Brook hart 2011), they argue that measures need to be constructed and analyzed in relation to contemporary assessment standards, Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023) noted that the 1990 Standards have become dated in two ways: (a) they do not consider current conceptions of formative assessment (that is assessment for learning), and (b) they do not consider the technical and social issues teachers face in constructing and using assessments within standards-based educational reforms. Accordingly, Brook hart identified revisions to the Standards in order to appropriate them for the current accountability context of education. a set of research-based principles and guidelines for assessing student learning in classroom contexts. In light of critiques directed at previous assessment literacy measures and based on recommendations to develop instruments based on contemporary assessment standards and practices Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023; Asiimwe & Magunda, 2023).

The study of Teacher Training Measurement and Assessment Measurement Skills conducted by Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023) that correlate with teacher assessment competence and use of flipped classroom model found out that teaching requires a complex set of measurement and assessment skills. These skills include the administration and interpretation of standardized tests, the ability to make rapid in-classroom assessment of student understanding and progress, the measurement of student achievement, assignment of grades, and the ability to explain assessment results to parents. Moreover, the diversity of skills needed appears to be increasing.

The Measurement of Teacher's Personality Competence and Performance Using Embedded Model conducted by Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe (2023) correlated to Personal competence of teacher and

uses of flipped classroom model revealed that, personal competence according to Joni, (2008) needs special attention, because most of the personality is not formed through direct learning in the context of formal education, but most are formed as a result of accumulated learning experience gained on preposition and previous education are formed even in a family environment. It is necessary therefore, personal competence observed with in-depth interview with mixed approach, while others competence is approached quantitatively. Teacher professionalism which is reflected in some of these competencies together with the compensation will determine the job satisfaction of teachers that will ultimately determine the performance of the teachers as well

According to Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asimwe (2023, the Act of the Republic of Indonesia No. 14/2005 on Teachers and Lecturers call for 4 teacher competencies, They are: pedagogical, personality, social, and professional; Those four component of the professional competences for teachers; simultaneously, competence variable determines the quality of teacher performance. The findings of the study show that the pedagogical, professional and personality competences have significant effect on the teachers' performance, while, social competence have no significant effect. Personality competence, based on the interviews, show that teachers, initially, have no interest for being a teacher, but they got interested and fun as the time goes by, so they perform well, it means that qualitative finding supports the quantitative approach findings. Lastly, the recommendations for the research findings is that the selection of recommended recruitment of teachers should be layered and covered, so that the job as a teacher will come from individual's heart / soul that means a personality from the beginning Way Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asimwe, 2023).

According to Kennedy and Powell (2022), Rytura, Serunjogi and Asimwe (2023) that conclude that, personal competence of Teachers have an important role to improve the quality of education which are required to have the expertise, competence and high professionalism for their duty. Professionalism is the condition, direction, values, goals and quality of expertise and authority relating to a person's livelihood. Theorized five individual elements of professionalism: 1) believe their work has an interest, 2) committed to the public good services, 3) the need for autonomy on the job requirements, 4) support self-regulation for their work, 5) affiliation with the profession members Way Long Que (2017) Stuebar and Idowu (2019) Personal relationship of Teacher and student in the flipped classroom studied by Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022), also linked with Personal competence of teacher and uses of flipped classroom model revealed that positive relationship between the and the student in efforts to gain trust and respect from each other.

This relationship may consist of getting to know your students better, providing choice and encouraging the students to become stronger learners every day. By doing this teachers are showing respect to their students, valuing their individuality and being polite. Having a positive relationship with your students helps them become more successful in the classroom as well as makes your classroom a safe and welcoming environment for all terms of physical development of learners, it is possible that the teacher, within school campus, where the online learning and ICT supports teaching learning process, it should often be targeted with the view that it does not ignore physical development of the students. However flipped classroom learning model in many school of Tanzania especially Zanzibar faced this limitation (Kennedy and Powell, 2022). It included school computers lab, internet, network where students get a lot of time for playing computer games, football physical work, classrooms inside and outside their school.

School with sufficient equipment's engages student satisfaction, motivation; successful acquisition of knowledge; course completion (persistence); course delivery methods; and faculty and institutional support. Although some authors compartmentalize the learning experience into what happens in the classroom others broaden their scope to include other variables, such as faculty and institutional support, financial aid, and quality of instruction Way Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asimwe, 2023).

3. Methodology and discussion

The study adopted a descriptive survey design, the designs is the most appropriate for the study because it describes facts and characteristics concerning individual, group or situation. The design was also picked based on (Bryman and Bell 2015), assertion that descriptive studies are designed to obtain pertinent and precise information concerning the status of phenomena and whenever possible to draw valid general conclusions from the facts discovered. The study used a mixed methodology approach, that is, quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative approach was used to collect and analyze numerical data through surveys using questionnaires and qualitative approach that was used to make observations, to get information through interviews to get the in-depth opinions of the respondents about the study, (Bryman and Bell 2015). The study was directed by Positivism Philosophy that adheres to the view that only "factual" knowledge gained through, descriptive survey study design, including both qualitative and quantitative characteristics, is trustworthy.

Table 1 Formative assessment ability in teaching lower Secondary School in Northern Region Zanzibar Tanzania.

Items	Mean	Std. deviation	Interpretation
Students' works are marked	1.91	.96289	Low
After marking, students' work is returned to them	1.63	1.05398	Very Low
Feedback is interactive	1.66	1.06565	Very Low
The teacher does allow students to send assignments to his/her e-mail	1.99	0.96679	Low
The teacher explains the grades given and provides a grading rubric	1.09	1.02546	Very Low
Average Mean	1.58	1.015	Very Low

Source: Primary Data, 2023.

The results in Table 1.0 on the formative assessment ability of teachers and flipped classroom model revealed that, the average mean of 1.58 which means very low. Students' works are marked have a mean of 1.91 which means low. After marking, students' work is returned to them has a mean of 1.63 which means very low. Feedback is interactive has a mean of 1.66 which means very low. The teacher doesn't allow us to send assignments to his e-mail has a mean of 1.99 which means low. The teacher explains the grades given and provides a grading rubric has a mean of 1.09 which means very low. On the other hand, Teacher in lower Secondary Schools of Northern Region of Zanzibar fail to manage, control and supervised their students while assessed under the flipped approach even if some students are so lazy that they want a person to coerce and force them. So, in a flipped classroom model, this may not be possible, hence becoming lazy and sometimes fail. During the interview the coordinators said that;

Many of teachers said that in flipped classroom approach 'enables students to do assignments well since their students have enough time. They have time for remembering cheating, copy and paste. In this stage, the students try to recognize and recall the information they receive un realistically grade; however try to understand the basic concepts and principles of the content they have learned.' But also face the challenges ensuring that students have access to resources outside of class, addressing technology limitations, ensuring students engage with pre-class materials, and designing effective in-class activities to reinforce learning. However the Republic Union of Tanzania try to distribute computers, telephones and tablets for all around schools country but the still problem on side of students

Also related to "the Flipped Classroom: Effects on Learning Outcomes and Student Satisfaction" Long Que (2017) Stuebar and Idowu (2019) Patrick, Kennedy, Chuk, Asimwe and Asimwe (2023) found that there was assessment misalignment: In the flipped classroom model, traditional assessments such as quizzes or exams may not align well with the active learning and problem-solving activities that take place during class time. This misalignment can create confusion or frustration among students and may not effectively capture their true understanding of the material. The study discusses assessment issues in the flipped classroom model. The study relates to that of Apiku and Asimwe (2023) Stuebar and Idowu (2019) Patrick, Kennedy, Chuk, Asimwe and Asimwe (2023) who suggest that technologically the success of the flipped classroom model heavily relies on the availability of technology and internet access for students to access the pre-assigned materials. Inadequate access to technology or unreliable internet connections can create difficulties for students in accessing the necessary resources. This challenge is highlighted in the article "Challenges and Opportunities in Implementing the Flipped Classroom Model in a Tertiary Institution"

In the study conducted by Long Que (2017) Stuebar and Idowu (2019) Patrick, Kennedy and Powell (2022) revealed that inadequate planning: Successful formative assessment requires careful planning and alignment with learning objectives. Teachers may fail to plan formative assessment activities that align with the pre-class materials and the desired learning outcomes. This lack of alignment can make it difficult to gather meaningful insights into student understanding and progress. Flipped classrooms require careful time management to balance the pre-class materials, in-class activities, and formative assessment. Teachers may face challenges in allocating sufficient time for formative assessment within the limited class time. This can result in rushed or ineffective formative assessment practices, leading to a failure to gather accurate information about student learning.

Lack of student preparation accounted as problem that effect the formative assessment in playing flipped classroom model, students are expected to come prepared to class after reviewing the pre-assigned materials. However, some students may not complete the required preparations, leading to a lack of understanding during in-class activities and assessments. This issue is discussed in "The Effects of the Flipped Classroom Model on Student Performance for

Advanced Placement High School Chemistry Students" by Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023).

Also wrote on The Flipped Classroom: A Course Redesign to Foster Learning and Engagement in a Health Professions School" recount that in active and uncare learning outside of the classroom: The flipped classroom model places a significant emphasis on students learning new content independently outside of class. However, some students may struggle with self-regulated learning or may passively consume the pre-assigned materials without fully engaging with the content. Lack of understanding or training: Teachers may not have a comprehensive understanding of formative assessment techniques or may not have received proper training on how to implement them effectively in a flipped classroom. Without this knowledge and skillset, they may struggle to design and implement appropriate formative assessment strategies (Long Que, 2017; Stuebar and Idowu, 2019; Patrick, Kennedy and Powell, 2022; Rytura, Serunjogi and Asiimwe, 2023).

Teachers during the interview reported that;

- *Unless successfully planned and executed, flipped learning model has big challenges are in technical aspects since it has a strong dependence on the technical resources or tools with which the learning experience is delivered. These tools need to be reliable, easy to use, and up to date, for them to have a meaningful impact on the learning experience.*

Table 2 Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient Analysis to Assess the Relationship between Formative Assessment Ability and Flipped Classroom Model in Teaching Lower Secondary Schools in Northern Region Zanzibar, Tanzania

Correlations				
			Formative assessment ability	Flipped Classroom Model
Spearman's rho	Formative assessment ability	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	0.648**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.000
		N	400	400
	Flipped Classroom Model	Correlation Coefficient	.0648**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.00
		N	400	400

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Results in Table 2.0 revealed that there is insignificant relationship between formative assessment ability and flipped classroom model in teaching lower secondary schools in the Northern Region of Zanzibar, Tanzania as shown by the sig value of 0.000. In other words, formative assessment does not affect the success of flipped classrooms in Zanzibar, therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no relationship between formative assessment ability and flipped classroom model in teaching is accepted.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The findings of the study showed that there was no relationship between formative assessment skills of teachers and flipped classroom model in teaching. This means that teachers are competent in terms of assessing students using flipped classroom model in teaching lower Secondary Schools in Northern Region, Zanzibar, Tanzania. The study recommended that formative assessment was found out to predict flipped classroom model as per the quantitative data, qualitative data revealed that assessment is hard to be done fairly through e-learning.

Therefore, the teachers after assessing the learners through the flipped classroom model should meet students in class (during face to face) and go through what was assessed. Why answer A was wrong and why answer B was right. This can cause the learners to understand things better. Education Board especially Zanzibar Education Council (ZEC) should ensure that teachers should be monitored regularly and post-supervision conference should always be arranged.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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